

Deliverable D3.1 Engagement with GIDE

Project Title	Founding a Global Image Data Ecosystem
Project Acronym	FoundingGIDE
Project Number	101130216
Project Start Date	01.01.2024
Project Duration	30 Months

WP Number & Title	WP3: Strengthening community coordination and Global Outreach
WP Leaders	UQ
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	6 - UQ
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Contractual Delivery Date	30.06.2026
Actual Delivery Date	30.06.2026
Authors	Maria Mirza, Yara Reis, Peter Bugeia, Lisa Yen, Koji Kyoda, Shuichi Onami
Contributors	Aiko Sekiguchi, Aastha Mathur
Reviewers	David Poger, Matthew Hartley, Antje Keppler

Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	19.02.2025	Maria Mirza	Initial draft
v0.2	26.05.2026	Maria and Yara	
v0.3	28.05.2026	Lisa and Peter	drafted Section 3.2
v0.4	9.06.2026	Maria Mirza	drafted Section 3.3, executive summary, KPIs and conclusion

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BiImage Archive
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBI	Global BioImaging
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
IDR	Image Data Resource
IDW	International Data Week
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SSBD	Systems Science of Biological Dynamics

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Engagement with Global BioImaging Community	5
2.1 Key activities and collaborations	5
2.2 Outcomes and insights	8
3. foundingGIDE Community Events	8
3.1 foundingGIDE Community Event in Japan	8
3.2 foundingGIDE Community event in Australia	11
3.3 foundingGIDE Community event in Europe	14
3.4 Community Events metrics and KPIs	17
4. Conclusion	19
Appendix 1 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2024 Program	20
Appendix 2 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2025 Program	24
Appendix 3 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2026 Program	29

Executive Summary

This report outlines the engagement with global imaging communities through global networks and dedicated annual community events. The foundingGIDE community events served as a platform for engaging local and global stakeholders and facilitating collaboration and coordination of global imaging data practices. These events brought together data producers, bioimage analysts, infrastructure providers, policymakers, funders, and industry representatives to discuss challenges and future directions for imaging data interoperability. The report also highlights the project's close collaboration with Global BioImaging (GBI), leveraging its international network of research infrastructures to bridge regional gaps, identify regional data management bottlenecks, and accelerate the worldwide adoption of imaging data standards. This collaboration directly supported the coordination of three global community events.

1. Introduction

Global collaboration is essential for advancing interoperability and standardisation in biological and preclinical imaging data. Effective sharing and management of bioimaging data remain significant challenges due to fragmentation across specialised domains and geographical regions. The foundingGIDE project aims to establish a Global Imaging Data Ecosystem (GIDE) by engaging diverse imaging communities, fostering interoperability solutions, and driving the adoption of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

2. Engagement with Global BioImaging Community

The foundingGIDE project aims to bridge existing gaps in global imaging data practices by engaging closely with the Global BioImaging (GBI) network, a worldwide community of imaging research infrastructures and core facility networks. Through this engagement, the project seeks to better understand regional and disciplinary needs and to disseminate project developments in a way that supports global adoption and interoperability of imaging data standards and practices. Leveraging established international networks while fostering new collaborations ensures broad participation in shaping an inclusive and globally connected imaging data landscape.

Global BioImaging is a mature international community that has connected imaging infrastructures worldwide for more than 10 years, bringing together partner networks across over 70 countries. It supports open access to imaging technologies by linking facility staff, imaging scientists, technology developers, funders and policy actors. A growing priority is image data, where Global BioImaging promotes good practices in image data management, standards, reusable analysis technologies and collaboration between image data repositories. Through foundingGIDE, Global BioImaging contributes to the foundations of a Global Image Data Ecosystem connecting biological and preclinical image data resources for metadata and data sharing. Recent activities, including image-data-focused webinars and the upcoming 2026 Exchange of Experience (October 2026) at EMBL Heidelberg, underline its role in advancing FAIR, interoperable and globally inclusive bioimaging data practices.

A key strategic approach has been aligning foundingGIDE activities with major Global BioImaging events, in particular by coordinating events back-to-back with the GBI Exchange of Experience 2024 in Okazaki, Japan, in M10. This approach maximised participation from both initiatives, enabling in-depth discussions on data interoperability, imaging infrastructure requirements, and community-driven metadata standards. It also provided a unique opportunity for cross-regional exchange between European, Asian, North American, Latin American, African, and other international stakeholders in imaging science.

In addition, foundingGIDE members actively contribute to GBI's working groups and regional initiatives, extending outreach beyond Europe and strengthening engagement with underrepresented regions, including Latin America, Africa, and Southeast Asia.

2.1 Key activities and collaborations

Global BioImaging Exchange of Experience 2024

foundingGIDE actively engaged with the Global BioImaging community during the “Exchange of Experience 2024: Image Data Horizons – Global Strategies for Accessible Knowledge”¹, where it co-organised its first Community Event back-to-back with the GBI meeting in Okazaki in October 2024 (see also below under 3.1). This joint organisation ensured strong overlap in participation and created a shared platform for discussion across initiatives.

The event served as an important space for:

- Identifying national and regional bottlenecks in image data sharing
- Sharing approaches to imaging data management across infrastructures
- Identifying barriers to interoperability at a global scale
- Discussing the role of metadata harmonisation in enabling cross-border data reuse
- Strengthening collaboration between imaging networks and data infrastructure initiatives

The back-to-back format significantly enhanced interaction between communities that are often geographically and structurally separated, fostering a more integrated dialogue on global imaging data challenges.

Global BioImaging International Working Groups

The Image Data Management Working Group:

Since project start (and in several cases even before) foundingGIDE partners actively take part in and contribute to the Global BioImaging Image Data Management Working Group, which focuses on advancing best practices and harmonisation approaches for imaging data management across infrastructures and core facilities. In total, the working group counts over 77 registered members from 20 unique countries, representing all inhabited continents.

Key discussion areas include:

- Metadata standardisation and interoperability
- FAIR imaging data workflows
- Data lifecycle management and repository alignment
- Imaging data sharing across institutions and regions
- Community needs for scalable and sustainable infrastructures

Through this engagement, foundingGIDE partners contribute expertise from imaging core facilities and international infrastructure networks, helping align technical developments with operational realities across the imaging community.

This collaboration also supported the launch of a webinar series in 2026 on Imaging Research Data Management (RDM) for core facilities², promoting capacity building and practical exchange on emerging data management practices across the global imaging community.

¹ <https://globalbioimaging.org/exchange-of-experience/exchange-of-experience-2024>

² <https://globalbioimaging.org/working-groups/image-data-management/gbispotlights-on-image-data-management>

Through these activities, the working group plays a key role in strengthening community capacity, promoting harmonised practices, and supporting the transition towards more open, connected, and sustainable imaging data infrastructures.

The Biomedical Imaging Community Working Group:

foundingGIDE actively contributes to the Global BioImaging Biomedical Imaging Community Working Group, which focuses on strengthening collaboration across biomedical imaging communities and supporting inclusive approaches to imaging data management. The group has 71 registered members from 31 unique countries, representing all inhabited continents.

A key activity under this working group was the organisation and contribution to a dedicated webinar on imaging data interoperability, bringing together experts from imaging infrastructures, data management initiatives, and international research networks. The webinar provided a platform to discuss challenges in interoperability, standardisation, and cross-institutional data sharing, while gathering feedback from the broader imaging community.

The outcomes of these discussions contributed to an EMBO Reports publication³, highlighting community perspectives on imaging data interoperability and the need for coordinated international action.

Latin American Imaging Scientists' Study Visit

From 9–13 September 2024, Global BioImaging (GBI) hosted a study visit at EMBL in Heidelberg, Germany. From 9–13 September 2024, Global BioImaging (GBI) welcomed imaging scientists, facility managers, and network coordinators from Argentina, Brazil, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, Paraguay, and Uruguay to EMBL Heidelberg, Germany, for a week-long study visit. The programme provided a platform to exchange expertise, strengthen regional and international connections, and address common challenges in microscopy, imaging technologies, and imaging data management⁴.

Discussions also focused on the growing complexity of imaging data workflows and the need to strengthen regional capacity in FAIR-aligned practices, including metadata standards, interoperable formats, and sustainable data repositories.

foundingGIDE presented its vision for a globally connected imaging data ecosystem, emphasising interoperability as both a technical and organisational requirement, and highlighting the role of regional initiatives in shaping distributed infrastructures.

As foundingGIDE works toward establishing a Global Imaging Data Ecosystem, global representation and engagement remain essential. The visit provided important insights into local regional constraints and opportunities, reinforcing potential collaborations in training, governance, and infrastructure alignment toward more equitable global imaging data ecosystems.

³https://link.springer.com/article/10.1038/s44319-025-00652-w?utm_source=rct_congratemail&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=oa_20251203&utm_content=10.1038%2Fs44319-025-00652-w

⁴ <https://globalbioimaging.org/news/seizing-global-networking-opportunities>

Life Science Data Infrastructures at International Data Week

foundingGIDE extended its community outreach by collaborating on a session at the International Data Week (IDW) Conference 2025, 13-16 October, in Brisbane, Australia, with the Life Science Data Infrastructures Interest Group of the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

This collaborative session showcased multimodal data integration efforts from major international infrastructures, including ELIXIR, EMBL-EBI, Euro-BioImaging, and Instruct-ERIC. The session explored emerging standards and best practices for integrating and sharing multimodal data, such as imaging, structural, and genomic data, within the framework of the federated Life Science Connect Node in the EOSC Federation (European Open Science Cloud).

foundingGIDE contributed critical perspectives from its ongoing foundational work to establish a GIDE, focusing the discussion on how the wider international community can effectively adopt GIDE outcomes. The discussions highlighted key challenges and strategic opportunities regarding interoperability across diverse platforms, standards harmonisation for multimodal data, and ontology alignment between biomedical and imaging domains.

Connecting with these non-image data resources and cross-disciplinary communities at IDW advanced the project's global outreach objectives, successfully engaging diverse stakeholders outside the core bioimaging domain to broaden the global data ecosystem.

2.2 Outcomes and insights

The engagement activities described above highlighted a clear and consistent community demand for greater harmonisation of imaging data practices and closer alignment of interoperability efforts across regions and infrastructures. They reinforced that progress toward FAIR imaging data depends not only on technical standards but also on sustained cross-community coordination, shared governance approaches, and targeted capacity building, particularly in underrepresented regions.

In this context, the activities revealed strong opportunities for convergence across existing initiatives, with foundingGIDE and Global BioImaging helping to foster a trusted and collaborative community around imaging data interoperability. Collectively, these efforts deepened mutual understanding of regional needs and global priorities, positioning GIDE as a connecting framework supporting a more integrated, inclusive, and scalable approach to imaging data interoperability.

3. foundingGIDE Community Events

The foundingGIDE Community Events served as a platform for engaging local and global stakeholders, fostering collaboration, and advancing image data interoperability through discussions on metadata harmonisation, ontology recommendations, and community-driven efforts. These three events (Figure 1) brought together data producers, bioimage analysts, infrastructure providers, policymakers, funders, and industry representatives to address current challenges and shape future directions for the GIDE.

Figure 1. Timeline of the three foundingGIDE community engagement events

Building a GIDE requires strong connections across the global imaging community. To support this aim, the foundingGIDE project organised three global community events throughout its lifecycle, creating opportunities for dissemination, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 2. Group photos from the three foundingGIDE community engagement events

These three global events brought together over 330 researchers, data producers, bioimage analysts, infrastructure providers, policymakers, funders, and industry representatives from 40 countries. Ultimately, these events were key to aligning international community efforts, gathering critical feedback on project outputs, and strengthening the global collaboration required to build the GIDE.

3.1 foundingGIDE Community Event in Japan

The first foundingGIDE Community Event (MS 6) was held in Okazaki, Japan, in 2024, back-to-back with the Global BioImaging Exchange of Experience 2024 (Figure 2). This event was instrumental in shaping the early discussions on GIDE and establishing a strong foundation for international cooperation.

The foundingGIDE Community Event in Japan brought together researchers, imaging specialists, core facility managers, funders, policymakers, and industry representatives to address global interoperability challenges in the imaging data ecosystem. Through presentations on metadata usage, interoperability frameworks, and infrastructure strategies, the event mapped current technology needs around image analysis, and directions for future developments in the global imaging data ecosystem (Figure 4).

Summary of the event

Date: 31st of October – 1st of November

Location: Okazaki, Japan

Theme: Connecting communities in the Global Imaging Data Ecosystem

Figure 3. Joint communication material for the back-to-back Global Biolmaging Exchange of Experience 2024 and foundingGIDE Community Event 2024

The agenda overview is available in [Appendix 1](#).

Figure 4. Joint program overview for the back-to-back Global Biolmaging Exchange of Experience 2024 and foundingGIDE Community Event 2024.

The event had three main sessions designed to explore the current landscape of the global imaging data ecosystem as follows:

- *Policy and Funders*: Addressing funding mechanisms, policy incentives for data sharing, and the role of international organisations in sustaining open science.
- *Ontologies and Metadata in Biolmaging*: Examining current metadata standards, challenges in harmonisation, and strategies for improving data discoverability.

- *Towards FAIR Image Data*: Discussing technological solutions, open-source platforms, and best practices for achieving FAIR data principles in imaging science.

Hybrid setup and recordings

Recordings of the event are available on [Euro-BioImaging's YouTube Channel](#).

Panel discussions

The Policy and Funders panel discussion explored the critical need for policies, sustainable funding, and collaborative strategies to enable image data sharing across disciplines and international boundaries. The session highlighted the need for compelling stories to illustrate the value of data reuse and stressed the importance of engaging skeptical biologists and the public through incentives, mandates, and policies to promote open data sharing.

The panel “Towards FAIR image data” explored the future of FAIR data, emphasising the need for practical steps, global collaboration, and a clear vision for the next decade. Key topics included metadata standards, open-source platforms, and the potential of large language models to enhance interoperability. The discussion underscored the importance of funder engagement, community-driven initiatives, and marketing the value of life sciences. Challenges such as data storage costs, ethical concerns, and the need for curated repositories and incentives for researchers were highlighted.

Breakout Sessions

The breakout session on *Sustaining and coordinating a Global Bioimage Data Ecosystem* emphasised bridging the knowledge gap between biological and data scientists, making data-sharing tools more user-friendly, and demonstrating the benefits of research data management. Challenges such as cultural resistance and the need for institutional policies and incentives were discussed, along with the importance of leveraging regional and global networks.

The breakout session on *Harmonising Metadata Models* discussions highlighted the need for a flexible yet structured approach to standardising metadata and dynamically updated community-driven metadata. Challenges such as the complexity of harmonising ontologies and data models and ensuring detailed metadata for imaging techniques were emphasised. The session underscored the importance of global leadership, long-term maintenance, and investment in metadata standards, calling for community input and collaboration to refine and implement these efforts effectively.

The breakout session *Working towards a GIDE: Community roles and opportunities* highlighted global disparities in bioimaging data management and sharing, emphasising the need for coordinated efforts to bridge gaps. Suggestions included fostering a culture of data sharing through ambassadors and top-down policy changes, particularly in under-resourced regions.

Participant Demographics

The event brought together more than 113 participants from 26 countries (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Geographical distribution and key participation statistics of attendees at the foundingGIDE Community Event 2024

3.2 foundingGIDE Community event in Australia

The second foundingGIDE Community Event (MS 5) was held in Brisbane, Australia, in 2025. This event was conveniently convened between International Data Week (IDW) 2025 and eResearch Australasia 2025, with foundingGIDE being co-advertised at IDW. Some speakers and attendees from IDW also spoke or attended foundingGIDE, while some attendees also went on to attend eResearch Australasia 2025.

Participant Demographics

See below for a summary of the geographical distribution of attendees (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Geographical distribution and key participation statistics of attendees at the foundingGIDE Community Event 2025

Summary of the event

This event presented an excellent opportunity to check on and review the status of the foundingGIDE deliverables at the mid-point of the project, and to bring together participants from across Australia and South-East Asia. It set foundingGIDE up for the final community event in Heidelberg in May 2026.

The event brought together researchers, infrastructure providers, and community members to explore the latest developments and challenges in imaging interoperability. Over 1.5 days, participants shared insights, discussed challenges, and collaborated on practical solutions for advancing the imaging data ecosystem.

The event was hosted by the Australian project partners, Microscopy Australia and National Imaging Facility, with a program that featured five plenary sessions, a dynamic panel discussion, and three hands-on workshops. The event was sponsored by [QCIF](#), [AARNet](#), and [Intersect](#), all Australian research infrastructure organisations.

Session Overview

Date: 17-18th October 2025

Location: Brisbane, Australia

Theme: Imaging Data Ecosystem: Towards Shared Solutions

Imaging Data Ecosystem – Towards Shared Solutions

Figure 7. Program overview for the foundingGIDE Community Event 2025.

Event program

See [Appendix 2](#) for the foundingGIDE 2025 event program.

Main sessions

The event had five main sessions designed to both explore the current global imaging data landscape, whilst looking at opportunities to further develop the ecosystem, particularly regarding future technologies, as follows:

- *Towards Shared Solutions*: highlighted global efforts to build interoperable and open imaging data ecosystems.
- *Metadata and Ontologies*: explored efforts to harmonise metadata models and ontologies to enable interoperability across biological and preclinical imaging, highlighting progress from the foundingGIDE BioImaging and Preclinical Stream and related initiatives.
- *Infrastructure to Manage Imaging Big Data*: explored how imaging infrastructures can support FAIR data management at scale, highlighting national and institutional strategies for handling rapidly growing imaging datasets.

- *Collaboration across disciplines and modalities*: explored how imaging facilities and infrastructures are advancing global collaboration, data interoperability, and metadata capture.
- *Infrastructure for Future Technologies and AI*: showcased global efforts to build imaging infrastructures ready for large-scale data integration and AI applications.

Hybrid setup and recordings

Recordings of the event are available on [Euro-Biolmaging's YouTube Channel](#), and the full program is available in [Appendix 2](#).

Panel discussions

The panel “What Drives Success in Community-Led Solutions?”, chaired by Lisa Yen and Wojtek Goscinski, explored what truly sustains and connects global, community-driven initiatives in imaging science. The discussion brought together a diverse group of panelists, Nathalie Gaudreault (Allen Institute for Cell Science, USA), Aastha Mathur (Euro-Biolmaging ERIC), Tomomi Shimogori (RIKEN Center for Brain Science, Japan), Hilary Hanahoe (Research Data Alliance), and Joe Shapter (The University of Queensland, Australia).

Breakout sessions

The community event included three 90-minute interactive workshop sessions to foster in-depth dialogue, identify challenges and co-develop pathways to greater interoperability across domains.

The three workshop themes were:

1. Harmonising Preclinical Imaging Data
2. Harmonising Biolmaging Data
3. Community roles and opportunities in the Global Imaging Data Ecosystem (GIDE)

The hybrid workshop session on *Harmonising Preclinical Imaging Data* chaired by Dario Longo, highlighted the urgent need for a standard metadata model to connect multiple, distributed preclinical image data repositories. Key barriers to sharing included a lack of willingness and standards, with suggestions to adopt minimum, FAIR-aligned metadata standards and include Research Activity Identifiers (RAiD) in ontologies.

The second workshop session, on *Harmonising Bioimaging Data* chaired by Shuichi Onami, reviewed the recommended metadata elements in foundingGIDE. The need for more comprehensive handling of compounds and analysis metadata was highlighted. Key future steps involve continuing an open discussion to gather feedback on the metadata recommendations and developing user-friendly tools for laboratory-level data input.

The third workshop session on *Community roles and opportunities in the Global Image Data Ecosystem* chaired by David Poger and Maria Mirza (in-person), and Yara Reis and Peter Bugeia (online), focused on three main areas: effective community activities, project sustainability, and identifying community partners. Discussions highlighted that successful community activities require accessible, usable, and adaptable standards and that effective standards often emerge from small, practical beginnings. A key adoption framework proposed was to progressively engage communities by making things possible, easy, normal and rewarding. Finally, the group identified potential community partners, including the AI communities, who are potentially end-users of foundingGIDE outputs.

Overall, all sessions stressed the importance of community engagement, standardisation, and developing practical tools to improve data discoverability and adherence to global guidelines.

3.3 foundingGIDE Community event in Europe

The third foundingGIDE community event (MS 3) served as the final community exchange for the effort to establish the foundations of the GIDE. Following its previous global community events in Japan (2024) and Australia (2025), the foundingGIDE third community event took place on 4-6 May 2026, hosted as a hybrid event at EMBL in Heidelberg, Germany. The event achieved significant engagement, gathering more than 100 in-person attendees and over 140 participants in total (Figure 8). The program featured more than 40 expert speakers distributed across 6 thematic plenary sessions over 2.5 days.

Participants from 30 countries

Figure 8. Geographical distribution and key participation statistics of attendees at the foundingGIDE Community Event 2026

Themed *From Interoperability to Global Impact*, the gathering brought together a diverse international cohort of researchers, infrastructure providers, data stewards, software developers, funders, and policymakers to consolidate the project's achievements and secure a sustainable future for the GIDE.

The plenary program (available in [Appendix 3](#)) was designed to address high-level challenges through six thematic sessions and two panel discussions (Figure 9). These sessions focused on aligning data sharing policies and funding strategies to move beyond regional silos, aiming to secure the long-term investment required for imaging data to become a permanent global research asset. A primary technical highlight was the project's successful effort to harmonise major repositories, specifically the BioImage Archive (BIA), Image Data Resource (IDR) and Systems Science of Biological Dynamics (SSBD).

Data Sharing Policy and Sustainability

This session explored sustainable frameworks to secure the long-term investment necessary for imaging data to become a permanent global research asset. Participants discussed how coordinated policy efforts can support the ecosystem's growth beyond a project's initial funding phase.

Technical Foundations of Global Data Sharing

Focusing on the core technical blocks of interoperability, this session provided a deep dive into metadata models and ontologies. The session highlighted the foundingGIDE project's achievements in harmonising major imaging repositories, including the BIA, IDR, SSBD:repository, and SSBD:database through the implementation of shared ontologies, the development of the common GIDE RO-Crate exchange metadata schema, and the launch of the centralised image data search

portal. The session also showcased ongoing technical developments within the global community to support image data interoperability.

Community Efforts on Global Data Sharing

Building on previous international exchanges in Japan and Australia, this session highlighted the vital role of global partners, such as Global BioImaging, in driving the GIDE. The focus was on fostering a culture of shared responsibility and moving the community from a mindset of data "ownership" to one of "stewardship". This approach is central to the project's goal of engaging diverse imaging research infrastructures and communities worldwide.

Data Sharing Across Domains

This session showcased how aligning practices across different scientific domains can promote cross-disciplinary discoveries. By promoting a harmonised approach to life science research, the session demonstrated the potential for broader scientific impact through integrated data ecosystems.

Figure 9. Program overview for the foundingGIDE Community Event 2026

Building Common Sustainable Solutions

This session featured presentations from industry representatives, who shared their perspectives on imaging data interoperability and emerging standards. The discussions highlighted the importance of collaboration between researchers, infrastructure providers, and industry partners to support the development of practical and widely adopted interoperability solutions.

Data Reuse and AI-Ready Data

As the demand for AI-driven discovery increases, this session examined the essential role of high-quality, well-annotated datasets and standardised metadata frameworks. Through real-world use cases, the session explored how FAIR imaging data is reused to accelerate scientific discovery. Discussions also emphasised ensuring that reused data remains a trusted and available foundation for future breakthroughs.

The final plenary session of the foundingGIDE Community Event 2026 provided a comprehensive overview of the project's major achievements and demonstrated the progress toward its core objective of enabling interoperability across bioimaging and preclinical image data resources. The

session also contextualised these technical achievements within the broader context of foundingGIDE's global community activities, highlighting the project's progression from its first community event in Okazaki, Japan, in 2024, through ecosystem alignment activities in Brisbane, Australia, in 2025, to the 2026 community event.

Plenary sessions recordings are available on [Euro-BioImaging's YouTube Channel](#).

Poster session

A poster session was held during the community event, providing participants with an opportunity to present ongoing activities, research results, and community initiatives relevant to imaging data interoperability and FAIR data practices. Following an open call for abstracts, accepted contributions were displayed during a dedicated networking session. The posters showcased a broad range of topics from across the global bioimaging community, fostering discussions among researchers, imaging infrastructures, data experts, and other stakeholders.

Panel discussions

The panel discussion on “*How can policy support global data sharing?*” provided an important strategic perspective on the policy, governance, and sustainability dimensions required to enable a globally interoperable imaging data ecosystem. Bringing together representatives from research infrastructures, funding organisations, scientific publishing, and international imaging initiatives, the discussion highlighted the increasing recognition of research data as a long-term scientific asset and a foundational resource for AI-driven scientific discovery.

Discussions emphasised that technical interoperability alone is insufficient without coordinated policy frameworks, sustainable funding mechanisms, and institutional incentives supporting FAIR and open data practices. Panelists identified several persistent barriers to large-scale data sharing, including cultural resistance, uncertainties surrounding data ownership and stewardship, uneven global participation, and the lack of long-term operational funding for research data infrastructures.

Overall, the session reinforced the importance of sustained international coordination between funders, publishers, infrastructures, and scientific communities to establish machine-readable, interoperable, and sustainable data-sharing practices aligned with global Open Science objectives.

Panel on “Global community efforts on data sharing”

The second panel discussion provided an international perspective on the practical implementation of a connected and interoperable GIDE. Bringing together representatives from regional imaging infrastructures, data repositories, and research institutions across multiple continents, the session highlighted both shared and region-specific challenges in enabling imaging data sharing.

Discussions emphasised that, while major technical foundations for interoperability are increasingly available, significant barriers remain at the organisational, institutional, and cultural levels. Panelists identified persistent challenges including limited local infrastructure capacity, insufficient investment in data stewardship and curation expertise, fragmented adoption of community standards, and the continued lack of aligned incentives for researchers to share and curate data. The discussion further highlighted disparities in resources and infrastructure readiness across regions, reinforcing the need for globally coordinated yet locally adaptable approaches to data sharing.

Participants stressed the critical role of funders, publishers, institutions, and international infrastructures in supporting sustainable and equitable data-sharing practices. Particular emphasis was placed on the importance of investing in human expertise through data stewards and curators,

alongside the continued development and broad adoption of interoperable metadata standards and ontologies. The panel also underlined the need to reduce barriers to data deposition and reuse through user-friendly workflows, trusted infrastructures, and clearer demonstration of the scientific value generated through open and interoperable imaging datasets.

Overall, the session reinforced the importance of sustained international collaboration and community-driven coordination to ensure that imaging data infrastructures remain globally connected, interoperable, inclusive, and capable of supporting future data-intensive and AI-enabled research.

Following the plenary sessions, the event continued with parallel workshops and a technical hackathon. The hackathon served as the project's final technical coordination event. The detailed outcomes of this event is discussed in D9.2.

3.4 Community Events metrics and KPIs

The key performance indicators (KPIs) utilized to evaluate the success and impact of Task 3.2 are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Key performance indicators across the three community events

Related KPI	Community Event in Japan	Community Event in Australia	Community Event in Europe	Min KPIs
Number of participants per event	113	82	141	at least 50
Number of imaging communities represented	>10	>10	>10	at least 5
Number of image data resources represented	11	11	11	at least 5
Number of countries represented	26	22	30	-
Number of continents represented	6	5	6	-

The tables below provide a clear, direct breakdown of the gender ratios across our three community events. To ensure a transparent overview of project representation, the data is split into two key categories: the expert panels (Table 2) and the general attendees (Table 3).

Table 2. Gender distribution of invited speakers across the three community events

Event	Female	Male	Other/Prefer not to say
First Community Event	29%	71%	0
Second Community Event	36%	64%	0
Third Community Event	39%	61%	0

Beyond raw attendance and community representation, tracking the demographic composition of these events was a central priority for monitoring the project's commitment to equity and inclusivity.

Table 3. Gender distribution of attendees across the three community events

Event	Female	Male	Other/Prefer not to say
First Community Event	37%	61%	2%
Second Community Event	34%	65%	1%
Third Community Event	40%	59%	1%

While achieving full gender parity remains an ongoing process across the global imaging landscape, these metrics highlight foundingGIDE's continuous efforts to foster fair representation. By actively working to balance genders across both general attendance and expert panels, the project demonstrates a commitment to building an equitable and inclusive space for all communities.

4. Conclusion

The foundingGIDE project has successfully brought together a diverse and geographically distributed community of stakeholders committed to improving the interoperability and reuse of biological and preclinical imaging data. Through active engagement with Global BioImaging networks, international working groups, regional initiatives, and three dedicated global community events across Japan, Australia, and Europe, the project established a truly global dialogue around imaging data interoperability. These activities provided valuable opportunities to identify common challenges, align priorities, gather community feedback, and build consensus on approaches to metadata harmonisation and ontology recommendations.

The engagement activities and community events demonstrated that the challenges associated with imaging data sharing are shared across regions, domains, and research infrastructures. At the same time, they highlighted a strong drive within the community to collaborate on common solutions and to contribute to a more connected imaging data ecosystem. Discussions consistently reinforced the importance of combining technical interoperability solutions with community coordination, policy support, and capacity building to enable long-term impact.

The three foundingGIDE Community Events played a central role in this process. Together, they provided a global forum for defining the vision of a GIDE, giving feedback on project outputs, and strengthening international collaboration. The events facilitated exchanges between researchers, infrastructure providers, data stewards, software developers, policymakers, funders, and industry representatives, ensuring that the developed solutions were informed by a broad range of perspectives and community needs.

Collectively, these efforts have laid important foundations for the GIDE. Beyond the technical outputs delivered by the project, foundingGIDE has established a global community committed to advancing FAIR imaging data. The collaborations and shared understanding developed throughout the project provide a strong foundation for sustaining and expanding these efforts beyond the lifetime of foundingGIDE, supporting future international initiatives and contributing to a more open, connected, and impactful imaging research landscape.

Funding statement

foundingGIDE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101130216. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for the

Appendix 1 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2024 Program

Connecting communities in the Global Imaging Data Ecosystem

Date: 31 October – 1 November 2024

Location: Okazaki, Japan | Online

Day 1: Thursday, 31st of October 2024	
12:30 – 14:00	Registration and Lunch
14:00 – 14:10	Shuichi Onami – <i>Opening and Welcome</i> Center for Biosystems Dynamics Research, RIKEN, Japan
14:10 – 14:20	John Eriksson – <i>Opening and Welcome</i> Euro-BiImaging ERIC, Finland
14:20 – 14:30	Aastha Mathur – <i>Introduction to GIDE</i> Euro-BiImaging ERIC, Germany
Session on Policy and Funders, Communities Moderator: Aastha Mathur	
14:30 – 14:45	Kazutsuna Yamaji NII, Research Center for Open Science and Data Platform, Japan
14:45 – 15:00	Lucy Collinson – <i>The volume EM community, and data in correlative and multimodal imaging</i> Francis Crick Institute, UK
15:00 – 15:15	Masanori Arita DNA Data Bank of Japan, National Institute of Genetics, Japan
15:15 – 15:30	Anne Plant – <i>Metrology Meets Data Sharing</i> National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA
15:30 – 15:45	Wojtek Goscinski – <i>An Overview of the Australian Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy</i> National Imaging Facility, Australia
15:45 – 16:45	Coffee Break
16:45 – 18:00	Panel on Policy and Funders, Communities Chair: Antje Keppler, Section Director at Euro-BiImaging ERIC and Global BiImaging Coordinator, Germany Panelists:

	<p>Shaofeng Hu, Director, Division of Science Policy and Basic Sciences, UNESCO, France</p> <p>Herbert Schaden, Vice President and Head of Global Academia Key Account Management, Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany</p> <p>Jo McEntyre, Deputy Director, EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, UK</p> <p>Masanori Arita, Team Leader, DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ), National Institute of Genetics, Japan</p> <p>Jan Ellenberg, Director of SciLifeLab, Sweden and Head of EMBL Imaging Center, Germany</p>
18:30 - on	Dinner

Day 2: Friday, 1st of November 2024	
08:30 – 09:00	Arrival
09:00 – 09:20	<i>Reflections on Day 1, preview of Day 2, and questions</i>
Session on Ontology and Metadata Moderator: Maria Mirza	
09:20 – 09:40	Matthew Hartley – <i>Image data interoperability with OME-NGFF, RO-Crate and linked data</i> EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, UK
09:40 – 10:00	David Poger – <i>The Australian PID Strategy and Roadmap – An opportunity in Microscopy Australia’s journey to FAIR and CARE</i> Microscopy Australia, The University of Sydney, Australia
10:00 – 10:20	Shuichi Onami – <i>Landscape analysis of metadata usage in major bioimage repositories</i> Center for Biosystems Dynamics Research, RIKEN, Japan
10:20 – 10:40	Thomas Close – <i>Frametree: mapping data trees onto frames for “in-place” analysis of large datasets</i> National Imaging Facility, The University of Sydney, Australia
10:40 – 11:20	Coffee Break
11:20 – 11:30	Susanne Vainio (Dario Longo) – <i>Developing preclinical image metadata models and ontologies</i> Euro-Biolmaging, Finland
11:30 – 11:50	Josh Moore – <i>OME2024 NGFF Challenge Results</i> German Biolmaging, Germany

11:50 – 13:00	Breakout Rooms (parallel sessions)
Breakout Room 1: <i>Sustaining and coordinating a Global Bioimage Data Ecosystem</i> Co-Chairs: Aastha Mathur, David Poger Focus: strategies for a sustainable GIDE, focusing on aligning efforts, preventing duplication, and promoting collaboration and inclusivity across the bioimaging community.	
Breakout Room 2: <i>Harmonizing Metadata Models: Bridging Efforts and Overcoming Challenges</i> Co-Chairs: Shuichi Onami, Matthew Hartley Focus: the technical challenges of harmonizing metadata models across bioimaging repositories with focus on the current landscape, and strategies for collaboration to ensure alignment.	
Breakout Room 3: <i>Working towards a GIDE: Community roles and opportunities</i> Co-Chairs: Yara Reis, Peter Bugeia Focus: how the bioimaging community can contribute to GIDE's success by identifying roles and collaborations, ensuring it aligns with global initiatives and community needs	
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
Session on <i>Towards FAIR image data</i> Moderator: Koji Kyoda	
14:00 – 14:25	Stefania Marcotti – <i>Data in the wild – field notes from a core facility</i> King's College London, UK (20 min + 5 min Q&A)
14:25 – 14:50	Caterina Strambio De Castillia – <i>Data Management and Sharing for everyone: from the Bench to the Community and back again</i> University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA (20 min + 5 min Q&A)
14:50 – 15:15	Aswin Naraynan – <i>Open data and open analyses in Neurodesk</i> National Imaging Facility, The University of Queensland, Australia (20 min + 5 min Q&A)
15:15 – 15:40	Adán Guerrero – <i>Challenges and Opportunities for FAIR Image Data in Latin American Bioimaging, Insights from the Data Science for Bioimaging Working Group</i> National Laboratory for Advanced Microscopy, National Autonomous University of Mexico (20 min + 5 min Q&A)
15:40 – 16:05	Toshiaki Katayama – <i>Tools for integrated data</i> Database Center for Life Science, Japan (20 min + 5 min Q&A)
16:05 – 16:40	Coffee Break

<p>16:40 – 18:00</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Panel on <i>Metadata, Ontologies and Towards FAIR image data</i></p> <p>Co-Chair: Josh Moore, German Bioimaging, Germany Co-Chair: Matthew Hartley, EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, UK Panelists: Shuichi Onami, Center for Biosystems Dynamics Research, RIKEN, Japan Nicholas Condon, The University of Queensland, Australia Perrine Paul-Gilloteaux, CNRS Nantes France Bio-Imaging, France Stephen Jett, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative Imaging Program Manager, USA Joy Owango, The Africa PID Alliance, University of Nairobi, Kenya</p>
<p>18:00 – 18:15</p>	<p>Aastha Mathur - <i>Future directions and GIDE Community Event 2025</i> Euro-BioImaging ERIC, Germany</p>

Appendix 2 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2025 Program

Imaging Data Ecosystem: Towards Shared Solutions

Date: 17–18 October 2025

Location: Brisbane, Australia | Online

Timezone: Brisbane, Australia (AEST)

Day 1 Friday 17 October 2025	
08:00 – 09:00	Registration
Session 1 <i>Towards Shared Solutions</i> Plaza P4/P5 Co-chairs: <i>Lisa Yen and Wojtek Goscinski</i>	
09:00 – 09:05	<i>Welcome and Acknowledgement of Country</i>
09:05 – 09:25	Lisa Yen and Wojtek Goscinski <i>Microscopy Australia and National Imaging Facility</i> National Imaging Facility and Microscopy Australia
09:25 – 09:35	Sudeep Das <i>Euro-Biolmaging and the European landscape</i> Euro-Biolmaging ERIC
09:35 – 09:45	Aastha Mathur <i>foundingGIDE: Towards a shared image data landscape</i> Euro-Biolmaging ERIC
09:45 – 10:15	Hilary Hanahoe <i>Data, data everywhere and not a drop to drink</i> Research Data Alliance
10:15 – 10:45	Tomomi Shimogori <i>From Genes to Discovery: How the Marmoset Brain Atlas Advances Global Neuroscience</i> RIKEN Center for Brain Science, Japan

10:45 – 11:30	Panel discussion on <i>What drives success in community-led solutions?</i> Co-Chairs: Lisa Yen and Wojtek Goscinski
11:30 – 12:00	Coffee Break
Session 2 Metadata and Ontologies <i>Plaza P4/P5</i> Co-chairs: Maria Mirza and David Poger	
12:00 – 12:20	Shuichi Onami <i>Metadata harmonisation in major bioimage repositories</i> RIKEN Center for Biosystems Dynamics Research, SSBD, Japan
12:20 – 12:40	Dario Longo <i>Towards FAIRification of preclinical image datasets</i> National Research Council of Italy, Italy
12:40 – 13:00	Marek Cebecauer <i>REMBI-DCAT-AP. Towards interoperability of bioimaging data</i> Heyrovsky Institute Prague, Czech Republic
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
Session 3 Infrastructure to Manage Imaging Big Data <i>Plaza P4/P5</i> Co-chairs: Thomas Close and Tomomi Shimogori	
14:00 – 14:30	Joe Shapter <i>What do we need to make the best use of our Imaging Data?</i> The University of Queensland, Australia
14:30 – 14:45	Rubbiya Ali <i>Making Imaging Data FAIR and Traceable: Automating Management with Persistent Identifiers and PITSCHI</i> The University of Queensland, Australia
14:45 – 15:00	Aswin Narayanan <i>Making analysis FAIR: Sciget.org a platform for scientific research</i> The University of Queensland, Australia
15:00 – 15:15	Siobhann McCafferty <i>How National PID strategies support international research</i> Australian Research Data Commons, Australia

15:15 – 15:30	Greg Bass <i>Scientific Image Data Management Ecosystem in CSL’s Global Research & Development Department: Design, Evolution, and Learnings in Industry</i> CSL Innovation, Australia
15:30 – 16:00	Coffee Break
16:00 – 16:15	Group Photo – P4/P5 Foyer
16:15 – 17:45	<p style="text-align: center;">Workshops</p> <p>Workshop 1: <i>Harmonising Preclinical Imaging Data – Plaza P3</i> Chair: Dario Longo</p> <p>Workshop 2: <i>Harmonising Bioluminescence Imaging Data – Plaza P5 (HYBRID)</i> Chair: Shuichi Onami</p> <p>Workshop 3: <i>Community roles and opportunities in the Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE) – Plaza P4</i> Chair: Maria Mirza</p> <p>Workshop 4 (ONLINE): <i>Community roles and opportunities in the Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE)</i> Co-chairs: Yara Reis and Peter Bugeia</p>
18:00 – 22:00	Social Event (casual) – P4/P5 Foyer

Day 2 Saturday 18 October 2025	
09:00 – 09:30	Registration
Session 4 <i>Collaboration across disciplines and modalities</i> <i>Plaza P4/P5</i> <i>Co-chairs: Aastha Mathur and Bryant Roberts</i>	
09:30 – 09:50	Nicholas Condon <i>IMB Microscopy, building tools, managing big data and connecting experts</i> The University of Queensland, Australia

09:50 – 10:10	Bryant Roberts <i>Mediaflux for Data Sharing: Enabling Greater Collaboration & Interoperability at Adelaide Microscopy</i> The University of Adelaide, Australia
10:10 – 10:30	Nathalie Gaudreault <i>Prototyping the Internet of Biolmage Data (IBID): The North America Image Data Sharing Initiative</i> Allen Institute for Cell Science, USA
10:30 – 10:45	Johan Gustafsson <i>Galaxy and WorkflowHub: Open Access to Large-Scale Image Analysis Workflows</i> Australian BioCommons, University of Melbourne, Australia
10:45 – 11:00	Workshops Wrap-Up
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee Break
Session 5 Infrastructure for Future Technologies and AI <i>Plaza P4/P5</i> <i>Co-chairs: Sudeep Das and Aswin Narayanan</i>	
11:30 – 12:00	Tim Olsen <i>Clinical Trials, AI, and Translational Research: XNAT's Expanding Frontier</i> XNAT Works Inc, USA
12:00 – 12:20	Ryan Sullivan <i>Beyond institutions, integrated (inter)national infrastructure for biomedical imaging data capture, movement, and analysis</i> Australian Imaging Service, The University of Sydney, Australia
12:20 – 12:40	Saori Tanaka <i>Human neuroimaging databases focusing on psychiatric and neurological disorders in Japan</i> Nara Institute of Science and Technology / ATR, Japan
12:30 – 12:45	Chung-Han Tsai <i>Scalable Research Data Infrastructure for Microscopy and Getting AI-Ready</i> Australian National University, Australia
12:45 – 13:00	Lisa Yen and Wojtek Goscinski <i>Closing remarks</i> Microscopy Australia and National Imaging Facility

13:00 - 14:00	Lunch
---------------	-------

Silver Sponsors

Bronze Sponsor

Appendix 3 - foundingGIDE Community Event 2026 Program

From Interoperability to Global Impact

Date: **4–8 May 2026**

Location: Heidelberg, Germany & **Online**

Timezone: CEST

Day 1 Monday 4 May 2026 In the ATC Klaus Tschira Auditorium	
12:00 – 13:30	Registration & Light Lunch and Coffee
13:30 – 13:40	Antje Keppler <i>From Interoperability to Global Impact: Welcome on behalf of Euro-Bioluming</i>
Session 1 Data sharing policy and sustainability Co-chairs: Aastha Mathur and Lisa Yen	
13:40 – 14:00	Jan Korbel EMBL, Germany
14:00 – 14:20	Michael Arentoft (virtual) <i>Data sharing policy and enablers – European Commission perspective</i> European Commission
14:20 – 14:40	Joe Shapter <i>Moving Forward on the Data Sharing Journey</i> Microscopy Australia
14:40 – 15:00	Thomas Lemberger <i>Driving data sharing policies in publishing at EMBO Press</i> EMBO, Germany
15:00 – 15:10	Group Photo
15:10 – 15:40	Coffee Break
15:40 – 16:00	Kanae Kurata (virtual) <i>Advancing AI for Science and Data Sharing: Japan's Initiatives</i> Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan

16:00 – 16:20	Jason Swedlow Biohub, USA
16:20 – 16:40	Emmy Tsang <i>The Hidden Cost of Data Sharing Mandates: Infrastructure Risk in the Age of Data Policy</i> Invest in Open Infrastructure
16:40 – 17:40	Panel discussion on <i>How can policy support global data sharing?</i> Chair: Antje Keppler
17:40 – 19:00	Poster session (See poster abstracts)

Day 2 Tuesday 5 May 2026 In the ATC Klaus Tschira Auditorium	
Session 2 <i>Technical foundations of global data sharing</i> Co-chairs: François Sherwood and Koji Kyoda	
09:00 – 09:20	foundingGIDE Bioluming Team <i>Search once, find everywhere: GIDE's federated bioimaging portal</i>
09:20 – 09:40	foundingGIDE Bioluming Team <i>Standard, schemas, ontologies and glue: how GIDE search actually works</i>
09:40 – 10:00	Dario Longo <i>Development of standards and protocols for the FAIRification of preclinical image datasets</i> National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Italy
10:00 – 10:20	Vladimir Ulman <i>Building Czech-Bioimaging Repository for the National Repository Platform</i> Masaryk University & Czech Bioluming, Czech Republic
10:20 – 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 – 11:20	Katy Wolstencroft <i>NL-Bioimaging: A Distributed FAIR Infrastructure for Dutch Bioimaging</i> Amsterdam University Medical Center, Netherlands
11:20 – 11:40	Chi-Li Chiu <i>Building an AI-directed Bioluming Data Infrastructure</i> Biohub, USA

11:40 – 12:00	Stefan Klein <i>Infrastructure for medical image analysis & AI research</i> Erasmus University Medical Center, Netherlands
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch
Session 3 <i>Global community efforts on data sharing</i> Co-chairs Yara Reis and Johanna Bischof	
13:30 – 13:50	Yara Reis Global BioImaging
13:50 – 14:10	Christopher Wood <i>From Fragments to Frameworks: RDM in Latin America</i> Laboratorio Nacional de Microscopía Avanzada-UNAM, Mexico
14:10 – 14:30	Arun Sharma <i>Biological Image Metadata Standardization: Opportunities, Challenges, and the Role of IBIA</i> Indian Biological Data Centre, Regional Centre for Biotechnology, India
14:30 – 14:50	Caterina Strambio De Castillia <i>Toward FAIR Bioimage Data from the Ground Up: The North American Landscape</i> UMass Chan Medical School, USA
14:50 – 15:10	Caron Jacobs <i>Bandwidth, Bureaucracy, and Belonging: Imaging Data Management Priorities From an African Perspective</i> University of Cape Town, South Africa
15:10 – 15:50	Coffee Break
15:50 – 16:10	Nicholas Condon <i>From Ownership to Stewardship: Cultural Shifts in Imaging Data</i> The University of Queensland, Australia
16:10 – 16:30	Dongmin Kang <i>Role of Korea Bioimage Data Repository (KBI) and activities of bioimaging data curation center (BDCC)</i> Ewha Womans University, South Korea
16:30 – 16:50	Andrea Lara <i>Emerging Local Innovations in Biomedical Image Data Sharing in Guatemala</i> Universidad Galileo, Guatemala

16:50 – 18:00	Panel discussion on <i>Global perspectives on contributing to a connected GIDE</i> Chair: Yara Reis
18:30 – 20:00	Dinner

Day 3 Wednesday 6 May 2026 In the ATC Klaus Tschira Auditorium	
Session 4 <i>Data sharing across domains</i> Co-chairs: David Poger and Daniela Aviles Huerta	
09:00 – 09:20	Bob Jones (virtual) <i>The European Open Science Cloud</i> EOSC Association and CERN
09:20 – 09:40	Beatriz Serrano-Solano <i>FAIR Image Analysis across Sciences</i> Euro-BioImaging ERIC Bio-Hub, Germany
09:40 – 10:00	Ryan Sullivan Australian Imaging Service, The University of Sydney, Australia
10:00 – 10:20	Peter Maccallum <i>Managing research data across disciplines, borders and time</i> ELIXIR, UK
10:20 – 10:40	Anna Klemm <i>Image Data at the BioImage Informatics Unit (BIIF) and SciLifeLab, Sweden</i> SciLifeLab, Sweden
10:40 – 11:00	Coffee Break
Session 5 <i>Building common sustainable solutions</i> Co-chairs: Claudia Pfander and Sudeep Das	
11:00 – 11:10	Yin Cai <i>Democratizing Biomedical Imaging Research with AWS Health AI and Open Data</i> Amazon Web Services, Public Sector Healthcare & Life Sciences, Germany

11:10 – 11:20	Norman Rzepka (virtual) <i>Visualization, annotation, sharing and processing of large images with Webknossos and OME-Zarr</i> scalable minds, Germany
11:20 – 11:30	Tim Olsen <i>XNAT: A foundation for a Global Imaging Community</i> XNAT Works Inc, USA
11:30 – 11:40	Eric Perlman <i>The role of cooperation in global imaging</i> Image Cooperative
11:40 – 11:50	Erin Diel <i>Turning Open Innovation into Production-Ready Bioimaging Platforms</i> Glencoe Software, Inc.
11:50 – 12:00	Sebastian Rhode <i>The CZI (Carl Zeiss Image) Format & Open Interfaces: How ZEISS Enables Sustainable, Interoperable Bioimaging Workflows</i> ZEISS Microscopy, Germany
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch
Session 6 Data reuse and AI-ready data Co-chairs: Beatriz Serrano-Solano and Dorothea Dörr	
13:30 – 13:50	Juan Antonio Vizcaino (virtual) <i>ProteomeXchange and MetabolomicsHub: Global initiatives for standardising open data practices in proteomics and metabolomics</i> EMBL-EBI, UK
13:50 – 14:10	Keith Brophy <i>Connecting Imaging Infrastructure: Federated Identity in a Distributed Research Network</i> Australian Access Federation, Australia
14:10 – 14:30	Kris Dreher <i>AI Readiness through Data Curation and Professionalized Annotation</i> Helmholtz Imaging, Germany
14:30 – 15:10	Coffee Break
15:10 – 15:30	Teresa Zulueta-Coarasa <i>Unlocking bioimage data for AI through the FAIR principles</i> EMBL-EBI, UK
15:30 – 15:50	Guillaume Gay <i>Biolmage Cloud through the underground</i> France Biolmaging, Université de Montpellier, France

15:50 – 16:10	Michele Darrow <i>Depositing Biological Segmentation Datasets FAIRly</i> Rosalind Franklin Institute, UK
Wrap Up 2.5 years of foundingGIDE	
16:10 – 16:20	John Eriksson, Antje Keppler, Linda Chaabane Euro-Bioluming ERIC, Germany
16:20 – 16:40	Aastha Mathur Euro-Bioluming ERIC, Germany

Day 4 Thursday 7 May 2026	
Workshops and Hackathon	
09:30 – 10:30	Registration and welcome for Workshops and Hackathon
10:30 – 12:30	Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i> Workshop Guidelines on providing Image Analysis as a Service [link] <i>in ATC Helix A01 Seminar Room</i> GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i>
12:30 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 – 15:30	Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i> Workshop Guidelines on providing Image Analysis as a Service [link] <i>in ATC Helix A01 Seminar Room</i> GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i>
15:30 – 16:10	Coffee Break

16:10 - 18:00	<p>Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i></p> <p>Workshop Guidelines on providing Image Analysis as a Service <i>in ATC Helix A01 Seminar Room</i></p> <p>GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i></p>
18:00 - 21:00	<p>Social Evening <i>ATC Rooftop</i></p> <p>Evening kindly sponsored by </p>

<p>Day 5 Friday 8 May 2026</p>	
<p>Workshops and Hackathon</p>	
09:00 - 10:30	<p>Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i></p> <p>GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i></p>
10:30 - 11:00	<p>Coffee Break</p>
11:00 - 12:30	<p>Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i></p> <p>GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i></p>
12:00 - 13:30	<p>Lunch</p>
13:30 - 15:30	<p>Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i></p> <p>GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i></p>

15:30 – 16:00	Coffee Break
16:00 – 17:00	Workshop Preclinical and Clinical Data Management and Analysis <i>in Flex Lab A+B</i> GIDE Hackathon <i>in IC Lecture Hall</i>